

**DIPLOMATIC AND TRADE-ECONOMIC RELATIONS BETWEEN THE KOKON
KHAN AND RUSSIA**

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Abstract: In this article, the Kokan khanate developed due to its favorable geographical conditions, located on the caravan routes and in an area with long-developed agriculture, and the city of Kokan was one of the largest cities of Central Asia in the first half of the 18th-19th centuries. The information about the fact that the development of a wide range of crafts in the Kokan Khanate made it possible to establish trade relations with neighboring countries is highlighted.

Keywords: trade, caravan routes, Umar Khan, handicrafts, paper, Moi Mubarak, Russia

The Kokan Khanate developed due to its location in favorable geographical conditions, on caravan routes, and in an area where agriculture had been developed for a long time. In the first half of the 18th and 19th centuries, the city of Kokan was not only the khanate, but also one of the largest cities in Central Asia. The city of Kokan was turned into the political, economic and cultural center of the khanate. There are large cities such as Kokan, Tashkent, Andijan, Namangan in the khanate, in which the field of handicrafts developed on a large scale. For example: Kokan had the following types of crafts. Coppersmith, goldsmith, engraver, gunsmith, potter, paper cutter, weaver, hat maker, embroiderer, bridge maker, blacksmith, baker, carriage maker, velvet maker, carpenter, painter, gilker, druggist, jibachi, devorzan, degrez, yormadoz, kutai, gunsmith, najjor, spearman, fencer, pillager, furrier, shoemaker, tubrez, paranjidoz, tent maker, chevar, Chitgar, carpet maker and hokozos. There was a market in the city of Kokan on Wednesdays and Sundays. The development of a wide range of crafts in the Kokan Khanate made it possible to establish trade relations with neighboring countries [1,94].

Relations between the Kokan Khanate and Russia began later than other khanates. The fact that the Kokan Khanate is located far from Russia did not allow for the establishment of relations. However, the Kokand Khanate established intensive diplomatic and trade-economic relations with Central Asian khanates, neighboring China, India, and Kyrgyz steppes. From the beginning of the 19th century, Russia began to look at the Kokan Khanate with great interest. In the 18th and 19th centuries, when paper production in Samarkand was declining, paper production began in Kok. The production of this product is connected with the migration of paper-making masters from Samarkand to Kokan. As a result, it would be safe to say that Kokan has become a monopoly engaged in the supply of paper from the Aral Sea to China. Kokan paper was taken to Kashgar and even to northern Afghanistan. The paper workshop is located next to the mausoleum behind the Moyi mubarak gate of Kokhan city. The paper mill consists of a simple palace, the area of which is 25-30 square meters, on one side of the porch there is a mill, and on the other side there is a large machine for paper pulp. With the help of his assistants, the master prepared 300 sheets of paper in one day. In addition to Kokan, paper was also developed in other places. But Kokan paper was far superior to them in terms of its quality and quantity. Central Asian scientists, historians, poets wrote their works on Kokan paper. These papers were widely used in the cabinet. Local

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manuscripts and various diplomatic documents were written on Kokan paper. Siberian Cossack Maksimov, who was in Tashkent at the beginning of the 19th century, wrote that paper is made in Kokan and Tashkent [2,28].

The size of Kokan paper was 58 cm in length and 50 cm in width. There are 240 sheets of it in a pack, on the eve and at the beginning of the First World War, the first type costs 6 rubles, the second type costs 4 rubles. and the third variety 3 rubles. standing There was also very good quality paper made of silk. Since tissue paper was very expensive, there was little demand for it. Tissue paper was prepared on a special order [3,147].

Kokan was connected with Central Asian khanates, China, India, Iran, Russia and other countries through caravan routes, and the khanate entered into intense trade relations with them. Russia's trade and political relations with the Kokand Khanate were at first slightly less developed than those of the Central Asian khanates. This situation can be explained by the fact that the khanate is far from Russia and is separated by the Tashkent principality. Trade and diplomatic relations between Russia and the Kokan Khanate began to develop rapidly from the second decades of the 19th century. Kokan relations with Russia were friendly in the early days, and both sides were interested in these relations. The issue of trade, economic and political-diplomatic relations between the Kokan Khanate and Russia is reflected in the reports of Russian ambassadors and tourists, as well as in special works. Russia's relations with Kokan were carried out through Siberia. On January 13, 1806, the Siberian Inspectorate informed the Russian Minister of Commerce N.P. Rumyantsev that he had sent a trade caravan to Kokan. However, the merchant returned from Turkestan before reaching Kokan. The next caravan of Kaluga merchants Ivan and Akim Sveshnikov, sent from Russia to Kokan, successfully arrived in Kokan Khanate in 1811. Ivan and Akim Sveshnikov, who had the opportunity to establish trade with the Kokan Khanate for the first time, were duly rewarded by the Russian government [4,223]. Due to the arrival of a trade caravan from Russia, Kokan Khan Umar Khan suggested to the Russian government to establish free trade relations through Siberia. Alexander I, who took advantage of the fact that this proposal was in the interests of the ruling circles of Petersburg, supported it. The Russian Empire attached great importance to strengthening economic ties with the Kokan Khanate, and sought ways to protect ambassadors and merchants from the Kokan Khanate [5,97]. According to H. Ziyaev, a major expert on Central Asian and Siberian relations, Shokirbek, the ambassador of the Kokan Khan who came to Russia, said that Kokan merchants would have free trade in the Russian Empire and trade relations between Kokan and Russia. stated that it is necessary to create conditions for development [6,50-51].

The Russian government has given special assignments to expeditions and embassies sent from Russia to Central Asia. In particular, in 1813, Philipp Nazarov, the translator of the Siberian Corps, came to Kokan, i.e. in Petropavlovsk, with the purpose of resolving the conflict caused by the murder of the ambassador of the Kokan Khan who was coming from Petersburg. As a result of F. Nazarov's trip to the Kokan Khanate in 1813-1814, the book "Zapiski o nekotorykh narodax i zemlyakh sredney chasti Azii" was published in 1821. The work has a historical-ethnographic character and reports on the trade relations of the Kokan people with Kashgar, China, Khiva, Bukhara and Eastern Iran. He participated in the ceremony of reception of ambassadors of Kokhan Khan and saw ambassadors from China, Khiva, Bukhara and other countries during the reception ceremony[7]. F. Nazarov writes about the city of Oratepa and admits that the people there live in mud (pakhsa) houses and weave fluffy shawls in their homes. It is stated in the work that the

inhabitants of Oratepa trade with Turkmens, Iranians, and nomadic Arabs in the areas belonging to Bukhara.

In 1826, an article published in the Aziatsky Vestnik magazine reported that Kokan residents were engaged in cotton and silk cultivation, and that Kokan people traded with China, Khiva, and Iran [8,229-230]. In 1828, ambassadors from Kokand, Sadr Gamal'dar Tursunkhoja Nayzakhoja and Khoja Mir Kurban Mamat Kasimov, came to the city of Omsk and offered to Russian Tsar Nicholas I to establish friendly relations between the two countries. came to hand over the label. The ambassadors were very well received in the Asian department and were told that the empire would protect the ambassadors and merchants from the Kokand Khanate, and they were also offered to strengthen and develop Russian-Kokand relations.

According to the agreement between the two countries, on August 12, 1829, N.I. Potanin was sent from Omsk as an ambassador to Kokan, accompanied by ambassadors from Kokan. He stayed in the city of Kokan for five months, and in 1830 he set off to return to his country. N. I. Potanin wrote down the events he witnessed during his travels [9]. His work contains various information about the political and socio-economic situation in the regions of the Kokhan Khanate, local roads, the structure of the military, religious traditions, and the world of plants.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above information, Kokan and Russia are interested in the establishment of friendly trade and economic relations between the two countries. It can be said that the feeling of interest served the development of embassy and trade between them. However, the friendly relations between Russia and the Kokand Khanate at the beginning of the 19th century changed to an atmosphere of hostility by the middle of the century. Russia's dream of conquering the Central Asian territories and then going to the legendary India caused it to start its invasion campaigns to the south. The initial march of Russia to the territories of Central Asia was aimed at the Kokand khanate, and this movement ended with the termination of the khanate.

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